

WETTABILITY OF CARBON FIBER TOWS

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ABSTRACT

Physical adhesion between Carbon Fibers (CFs) and polymer matrices as well as the formation of voids at the interface between these two materials are mostly controlled by the wetting properties of the fibers. Due to the hierarchical structure of CF reinforcements, it is essential to study their wetting behavior at different scales: from the single fiber (microscale) to the fabric (macroscale) via the tow scale (mesoscale). In this work, we first developed a new methodology combining a tensiometric method and a synchronized in-situ optical observation technique to better characterize the wettability of CF tows. We then used it to evaluate the difference in wettability between tows composed of unsized and sized (T300) CFs. By comparing their wettability at the micro- and mesoscale, we could quantify how the modification of the surface chemistry at the microscale is transferred to the mesoscale.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibers (CFs) have attracted great attention as an outstanding reinforcement for polymer composites because of their superior mechanical properties [1]. Nowadays, CFs have been widely used in many fields, from civil to industrial. However, the final mechanical properties of carbon-fiber-reinforced polymer composites (CFRP) depend not only on the intrinsic properties of the reinforcing CFs and polymer matrices, but also on the interfacial properties between these components [2]. Physical adhesions between CFs and polymer matrices as well as the formation of voids at the interface between these two materials are mostly controlled by the wetting properties of the fibers. Due to the hierarchical structure of CF reinforcements, it is essential to study their wetting behavior at different scales: from the single fiber (microscale) to the fabric (macroscale) via the tow scale (mesoscale).

The wettability of CFs with polymers can, for example, be revealed by measuring contact angles made by liquid polymers or probe liquids on fibers. Typically, contact angle measurements are conducted at the microscale, measuring the contact angle made by liquids around one monofilament or several parallel aligned fibers, using the Wilhelmy balance method [3], or at the macroscale, measuring the contact angles of a liquid droplet on surfaces of CF fabrics by optical methods [4]. A previous study[3] showed the difficulties of precisely measuring contact angles on a single CF due to its micrometer-scale diameter. It is also very difficult to independently and reliably evaluate the effects of surface chemistry and textile structure from the analysis of drop shape at the macroscale. CF tows show an intermediate and interesting case study, as their simple geometry, compared to fabrics, may not totally obscure the role of the surface chemistry. In addition, their large dimensions, compared to a single fiber, should ease the measurement of contact angles.

Probing the wettability of CF tows, is however highly challenging, because it couples the effects of surface chemistry and geometry of the fiber assembly characterized by spontaneous capillary wicking and elasto-capillarity induced aggregation. Therefore, in this work we first developed a new methodology combining a tensiometric method and a synchronized in-situ optical observation technique to better characterize at the same time the porosity of the tow and the external contact angles.

The K100SF tensiometer was used to measure the forces exerted by the liquid on the tows. Capillary wicking in the inter-fiber space and the formation of a meniscus around the tow are taking place quasi instantaneously when the tows contact the liquid [5]. The detected forces combine the weights of the imbibed liquid inside the tow and the meniscus formed around the tow. As to which process dominates is further investigated by analyzing the force data following the Washburn and Wilhelmy methods. Meanwhile, a digital microscope camera was used in combination with the tensiometer to capture in real time images of the meniscus around the tows. These gave external contact angles and the variation of the tow diameters at various wetting positions along the sample height by image analysis.

We then used these methodologies to evaluate the difference in wettability between tows composed of unsized (provided by Deakin University) and T300 CFs (product No.: FT300-3000-40A, commercially available sized CF tows purchased from Toray CFs Europe S.A.). By comparing their wettability at the micro- and mesoscale, we could quantify how the modification of the surface chemistry at the microscale is transferred to the mesoscale. Moreover, contact angles of CFs at meso- and microscale have been successfully linked by using the modified Cassie–Baxter model. The wettability of CF tows can thus be predicted from the contact angle obtained at the microscale. The effect of surface sizing on fiber wettability at mesoscale was assessed, which will enable better prediction and optimization of adhesion between a given polymer matrix and CFs at tow level.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Materials

The CFs are laboratory made unsized and untreated CF tows provided by Deakin University and commercially available sized CF tows named FT300-3000-40A (T300) purchased from Toray CFs Europe S.A, respectively. The unsized CFs were produced at Deakin University from commercial PAN precursor but skipping the sizing step. One T300 CF tow contains 3000 filaments with density of 1.76 g/cm^3 . The wetted T300 CF and unsized CF tows are around $600\mu\text{m}$ and $300\mu\text{m}$ in diameter respectively.

Before the wetting tests, the CF tows were washed in ethyl alcohol and dried at 80°C for 1h to obtain a clean surface by removing dust and grease without altering the CF sizing. The tows were then cut into pieces (20 mm in length) and each piece was clipped firmly into a holder that could be installed directly in the tensiometer.

The main properties of the test liquids (n-hexane: Acros; Deionized water: Millipore Direct Q-3 UV) are listed in Table 1.

Table 1 Test liquid properties.

Test liquid	γ_{LV} (mN/m)	ρ (g/cm ³)	Purity
n-hexane	18.4	0.659	99.6%
Deionized water	72.8	0.98	$18.2 \Omega \cdot \text{cm}$ resistivity

2.2. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

The surface morphology of unsized and T300 carbon fibers was observed in a FEI XL30 FEG scanning electron microscope to check the effect of sizing on the surfaces and the diameters of single carbon fiber samples. The fibers were dried to remove the water on the surface and then attached by double sided adhesive tape to the SEM stage. The immersed sections were imaged under a voltage of 12 kV.

2.3. Single fibers contact angle measurement (Wilhelmy method)

The method proposed by Qiu et al. [3] for measuring dynamic contact angles was used in this study to characterize the wettability of unsized single CFs with deionized water according to the Wilhelmy

method. A high-precision force tensiometer – Krüss K100SF (Krüss GmbH, Hamburg, Germany) was used to measure the forces exerted on a single CF during the dynamic wetting test. The K100SF tensiometer has a claimed weight resolution of 0.1 µg with testing velocities ranging from 0.1mm/min to 500mm/min. During the measurements, the fiber is stationary and the vessel holder moves up (advancing cycle) and down (receding cycle). A sketch of the apparatus is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Schematic of the experimental setup showing the combination of tensiometry and optical methodologies to characterize the wettability of CF tows.

Four fibers were tested by this method in case of the unsized CFs (contact angles for sized T300 fibers were taken from [3]). Each fiber was repeatedly dipped in and withdrawn from the liquid vessel three times at a velocity of 3.6 mm/min to measure a series of dynamic advancing and receding contact angles. Qiu et al. [3] suggested that dynamic advancing contact angles measured below 20 mm/min can be recognized as static advancing contact angles.

2.4. Carbon fiber tow contact angle measurements (optical technique)

A Motic SMZ-171 microscope and Moticom (CMOS) digital microscopy camera was used in combination with the tensiometer to capture in real time (every 500 ms) images of the formation of the meniscus around the tows. This gave access to external contact angles and the variation of the tow diameters at various wetting positions along the sample height. The pixel size was 3.24µm.

The optical analysis followed a two-step procedure: first, the pictures were analyzed with Tracker software [6] to determine the local tow diameter d and meniscus height z by locating the position of two contact points, as shown in Figure 2. The meniscus height is defined as the average value of height differences between these two contact points and the baseline. The contact angle is then calculated using the James equation [7], which models the height of a static meniscus made by a liquid around a cylindrical substrate:

$$z \approx r \cos \theta_{ex}^o \ln \left[\frac{4a}{r(1 + \sin \theta_{ex}^o)} - \delta \right] \quad (1)$$

where r is the local radius of the tow, $a = \sqrt{\gamma_{LV}/\rho g}$ the capillary length of the probe liquid (with ρ the liquid density, and g the gravity acceleration), and δ the Euler constant ($\delta \approx 0.58$).

Figure 2. In-situ observation of the meniscus formed between a T300 CF tow and

2.5. Carbon fiber tow contact angle measurements (tensiometric technique)

The K100SF Tensiometer was used to measure the forces exerted by the liquid on the tows. During a test, the tows were slowly soaked in the liquid over a length of 1mm and stopped at that position for 500s to make sure the external meniscus around the tow reached a static configuration. The vessel was then moved down until complete withdrawal from the liquid bath. The weight of liquid left in the tow was finally measured. The forces exerted on the tows were detected continuously every 200ms by the microbalance during the whole procedure (including approaching, wetting and withdrawing from the liquid bath). Six samples were tested for both unsized and T300 CF tows. As illustrated in Figure 3, capillary wicking in the inter-fiber space and the formation of a meniscus around the tow are taking place quasi instantaneously when the tows contact the liquid [5]. The detected forces combine the weights of the imbibed liquid inside the tow and the meniscus formed around the tow. As to which process dominates is further investigated by analyzing the force data following the Washburn and Wilhelmy methods.

Figure 3. (a) Schematics of a meniscus formed around a CF tow, θ_{ex}^f is the external apparent contact angle determined by the Wilhelmy method. (b) Schematics of internal capillary wicking between CF filaments. θ_a is the effective internal advancing contact angle determined by the Washburn method [8, 9].

As described in section 2.2, the weight of the external meniscus around a tow measured by the tensiometer can be analyzed by the Wilhelmy method. The weight of liquid (W_r) left inside the tow after complete withdrawal from the water bath was subtracted from the total measured forces to account for the effect of water up-take. It is assumed that this force characterizes the volume freely accessible to water inside the tow, i.e. the tow porosity. As already reported from single capillary tube wetting experiments, it is known that an external meniscus takes much less time than an internal one to reach equilibrium [10]. Therefore, although the external meniscus did already reach its static configuration at the beginning of the test, the liquid still kept wicking through the tow until the inter-

fiber space was fully filled by the liquid. Hence, the force data detected after the full wicking process were used to calculate external contact angles [11, 12].

$$F_{measured} - W_r = L_{tow} \gamma_{LV} \cos \theta_{ex}^f \quad (2)$$

where θ_{ex}^f is the external contact angle obtained from the force measurement, L_{tow} is the wetted perimeter of CF tow obtained by the camera.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Surface morphology of CFs

Figure 4 shows SEM pictures of unsized and T300 carbon fibers exhibiting a rough, ditch like structured surface. Comparing to the surface of unsized carbon fiber, the sizing agents on T300 carbon fibers do not change the surface morphology significantly.

Figure 4. SEM image of the surface of a single carbon fiber: a), b) T300 CF tow; c) T300 CF single fiber d) Unsized CF single fiber

3.2 Contact angles of CFs – fiber scale

Figure 5 shows the distribution of the dynamic contact angle results. An average advancing contact angle of $79.0 \pm 4.8^\circ$ was obtained, i.e. unsized single CFs are, as expected, more hydrophobic than the T300 single CF, which showed a static advancing contact angle with deionized water of $65.8 \pm 2.9^\circ$ [3]. Similarly, the receding contact angle of unsized single CF with an average value of $41.7 \pm 7.1^\circ$ is significantly larger than the one obtained for the T300 CF fiber with values between 20° and 0° [3]. The measured receding contact angle value of unsized CF in water is somewhat smaller than the value reported by Bismarck et al. ($56.3 \pm 3.1^\circ$) [13]. Moreover, all the values of contact angles followed Gaussian distributions indicating the reliability of the comparison between the two surfaces (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Distributions of dynamic contact angle values (unsized CFs with water).

3.3 External contact angles – tow scale

As shown in Figure 6, comparison between the results obtained from the force and optical methods for both unsized and T300 CF tow shows good agreement indicating that the combination of the force and optical methods successfully quantifies the effects of deformations and water up-take within the CF tows on the external contact angles. Figure 7 shows the average results obtained for the T300 and unsized CF tows. Moving from an unsized CF to a T300 CF, the static advancing contact angle decreases by $13.2 \pm 5.6^\circ$. The external contact angle around CF tows decreases more significantly ($19.1 \pm 7.0^\circ$), which indicates that the wettability of CFs at the mesoscale is not only affected by the surface chemistry properties but also by the structure of the tow.

Figure 6. External menisci formed after 200s and comparisons between the external contact angles obtained at this moment by the force and optical methods for the unsized and T300 tows.

Figure 7. Comparison of static advancing contact angles between unsize CF tows and T300 CF tows with water (static advancing contact angle of T300 single CF is from reference [3])

3.4 Relationship between the static contact angles at micro- and mesoscales

The difference in static advancing contact angles between single CFs and CF tows indicates that the wettability of CFs changes when moving from the microscale to the mesoscale. As CF tows are considered to be porous, the surfaces around them can be recognized as a composite surface made of CFs and air or fluid, respectively before and after contact with the fluid. As shown in Figure 8 a) and b), the contact line around the CF tow is not straight, which confirms that the external contact angle characterizes an heterogeneous surface composed of CFs and fluid in between them (after contact with the fluid). The Cassie law [14] is a widely used model [15] describing the contact angles of liquid on chemically heterogeneous surfaces. It gives the contact angle corresponding to the minimum free energy configuration, which is expressed in terms of the contact angles for each pure substrate. According to the modified Cassie–Baxter equation [35]:

$$\begin{aligned} \cos \theta_{CB} &= f_s \cos \theta_s + f_i \cos \theta_i \\ &= f_s \cos \theta_s + (1 - f_s) \cos \theta_i \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

with f_s the fraction of solid/water interface, when immersed in water. Traditionally, $f_i = (1 - f_s)$ represents the fraction of air/water interface with then $\theta_i = 180^\circ$. Here, as the tows are infiltrated by water, air is replaced by water so that f_i is the fraction of water/water “interface” with $\theta_i = 0^\circ$. θ_{CB} is the calculated “average” external contact angle around a CF tow. θ_s is the contact angle on the single CF. Figure 8 c) models the cross-sectional view of a triangle-packing arrangement of CFs in a wetted CF tow. If we assume that CFs have a regular triangle-packing arrangement and the area fraction of pores (P') at the cross-section is equal to the non-solid volume fraction (P), then P' can be described as follows:

$$P' = 1 - \frac{S_{CFs}}{S_{Total}} = 1 - \frac{\frac{\pi}{2} r^2}{\frac{1}{2} (2r + 2d')^2 \cos 30^\circ} = P \quad (4)$$

Where d' characterises the distance between two CF filaments, S_{CFs} is the cross-sectional area of the CFs in a triangularly packed cell, S_{Total} is the total area of this triangular cell. Hence, d' can be calculated by substituting r and P into Equation 8.

Then, Figure 8 d) depicts the cell of the outermost layer of CFs exposed to air. The liquid meniscus between two CF filaments is modeled as a straight line where θ_s is an adjustable contact angle. A similar model has already been successfully applied for nanofiber yarns [16]. Therefore, the solid to water fraction f_s can be calculated by:

$$f_s = \frac{d_s}{d_s + d_i} = \frac{d_s}{r + d'} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{and } d_s = r \sin \theta_s \quad (6)$$

Finally, θ_{CB} can be evaluated using Equations (3)-(6). The calculated values of θ_{CB} (Table 2) are close to our experimental results shown in Figure 8 for both the T300 and unsized CF tows. Therefore, the contact angles of CFs at the meso- and microscales can be linked by using the Cassie–Baxter model and a known non-solid volume fraction. Besides, this model also describes how the structure of the tows (porosities or distances between two CF fibers) can influence the wettability of the CFs at the mesoscale.

Table 2 Calculated external contact angles (θ_{CB}) and the parameters used for calculation

Type of CF tow	Non-solid volume fraction, P	θ_s	d' (μm)	f_s	θ_{CB}
T300 CFs	$54 \pm 3\%$	$65.8 \pm 2.9^\circ$	1.4 ± 0.2	$65 \pm 3\%$	$51.9 \pm 2.5^\circ$
Unsize CFs	$46 \pm 15\%$	$79.0 \pm 4.8^\circ$	1.0 ± 0.6	$76 \pm 11\%$	$67.4 \pm 6.5^\circ$

Figure 8. a) Picture showing the contact-line between water and a T300 CF tow. b) Schematics of the contact-line on the heterogeneous surface of a wetted CF tow (with liquid in between the CFs). c) Schematics of pore areas in a cross-sectional view perpendicular to the tow axis, where r is the radius of CF and $2d$ is the distance between two filaments. d) Cell of the outermost layer of CFs exposed to air, where θ_s is the static advancing contact angle of liquid with single CF.

4 CONCLUSION

This study aims at characterizing the wettability of unsized and T300 CFs (microscale) and CF tows (mesoscale). At the microscale, the wettability of unsized single CFs was first studied by precisely measuring dynamic contact angles and then comparing them with the wettability of single T300 CFs (from previous work). The static advancing contact angle of water on unsized single CFs at a low test velocity (3.6 mm/min) is $79.0 \pm 4.8^\circ$, which indicates that the unsized CFs are more hydrophobic than the T300 CFs (contact angle $65.8 \pm 2.9^\circ$). The receding contact angle of water on unsized CFs ($41.7 \pm 7.1^\circ$) is significantly larger than the one measured for the T300 CFs, with a value between 0° and 20° .

The combination of the force method and optical analysis permitted to better characterize the external contact angles. This innovative method provided consistent results between the externally optically observed contact angle and the contact angle obtained from the Wilhelmy force, by correcting for the absorbed liquid. For wetted T300 CF tows, the external contact angles are $46.0 \pm$

6.1 ° (force method) and 48.8 ± 3.2 ° (optical method) respectively; and for the unsized CF tow, the external contact angles are 65.1 ± 3.5 ° (force method) and 64.0 ± 3.4 ° (optical method) respectively. The effect of surface sizing on fiber wettability at mesoscale was therefore assessed, which will enable better prediction and optimization of adhesion between a given polymer matrix and CF tows.

Moreover, contact angles of CFs at meso- and microscales have been successfully linked by using the modified Cassie–Baxter model. By taking into account that the observed tow contact angle is determined by the fraction of solid surface versus imbibed liquid surface (for the wetted tow, and very likely by the surface fraction of solid surface versus air for the un-wetted tow), the solid contact angle can be obtained and this contact angle appeared to be very close to the contact angle measured at the microscale. The wettability of CF tows can thus be predicted from the contact angle obtained at the microscale.

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